

Synthesis and Biological Activity of 1-(4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetyl)-4-alkylthiosemicarbazides, -1,3,4-thiadiazoles and -1,2,4-triazoles

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Manuscript received 23 June 1994, accepted 27 October 1994

Thiosemicarbazides are convenient intermediates for the synthesis of 1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazoles. They are also known for their various biological activities¹. In view of these and in continuation of our work in this area, the syntheses of some new heterocyclic compounds containing thiadiazole or triazole and benzopyranone nucleus are reported here.

The 4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetamide (**2**) prepared² via alkylation of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin with chloroacetamide, was hydrolysed to give 4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetic acid (**3**). Esterification³ of **3** with methanol in acid medium gave the corresponding methyl (4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetate) (**4**). The ester (**4**) on condensation with hydrazine hydrate in absolute alcohol gave the corresponding 4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxo-acetylhydrazine (**5**), which was reacted with alkyl isothiocyanates to get the corresponding 4-alkyl-1-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetyl)thiosemicarbazides (**6a-c**). 2-Alkylamino-5-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxomethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (**7a, b**) was obtained by the cyclodehydration of **6** with phosphoric acid. The structure of **7** was also established via reaction of **5** with alkyl isothiocyanates in boiling acetic acid. The 5-mercapto-4-alkyl-3-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxomethyl)-1,2,4-triazoles (**8a, b**) were obtained by refluxing **6** with 2 N NaOH. The thiols (**8**) when treated with methyl iodide in presence of sodium acetate⁴ in acetone formed the 5-methylthio-4-alkyl-3-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxo-methyl)-1,2,4-triazoles (**9a, b**).

Biological activity : Using ethanolic solution with JICS-9

different concentrations, the compounds were tested for insecticidal activity against mosquito larvae. Twenty larvae of mosquito were used for one compound at different concentrations (5, 10, 15 ppm) in each experiment. Compounds **6b**, **7a, b** and **8b** at 15 ppm level showed 70, 70, 95 and 55% mortality.

Experimental

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses. M.ps. were determined using a Fisher-John's apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman 33 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on Varian T 60 (60 MHz) and Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) instruments using TMS as internal reference.

4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetamide (2) : A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol), chloroacetamide (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g) in dry acetone (100 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 15 h, then cooled and poured in water. The resulting solid was crystallised (78%), m.p. 235° (EtOH); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 390, 3 210 (NH₂), 1 715 (CO of pyrone), 1 695 (CO of amide) and 1 605 cm⁻¹ (C=C).

4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetic acid (3) A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol) and 1N NaOH (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. It was then acidified to pH1 with concentrated HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised (68%), m.p. 207° (MeOH); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 470–2 870 (OH), 1 730–1 705 (CO of α -pyrone and COOH), 1 610 (C=C) and 1 405 cm⁻¹ (C–OH).

Methyl 4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetate (4) : A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol), absolute

Scheme 1

methanol (3 ml) and dry benzene (6 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath, sulphuric acid (0.5 ml) added dropwise during refluxing and the reflux continued for 12–14 h. The mixture was then cooled and extracted with ether and ether layer dried and distilled under reduced pressure to yield the product (75%), m.p. 123° (EtOH); ν_{max} 1 745 (CO of ester), 1 715 (CO of α -pyrone), 1 605 (C=C) and 1 220, 1 210 cm^{-1} (ether linkage); δ (CDCl_3) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.1 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.5 (2H, br s, OCH₂) and 6.5–7.5 (4H, m, ArH).

4-Methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetylhydrazone (5): A mixture of 4 (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The product obtained after cooling was dried and crystallised (63%), m.p. 205° (BuOH); ν_{max} 3 420, 3 210 (NH₂), 3 280 (NH), 1 715 (CO of α -pyrone), 1 690 (CO of acid hydrazide) and 1 605 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ (CF_3COOD) 2.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.3 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 5.1 (2H, br s, NH₂), 6.5–7.4 (4H, m, ArH) and 10.3 (1H, br s, CONH).

4-Alkyl-1-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxoacetyl)thiosemicarbazides (6a-c): A mixture of 5 (0.01 mol) and alkyl (Me/Et/Ph) isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) was refluxed in butanol (50 ml) for 4 h. The product obtained after cooling was dried and crystallised from butanol, (80–85%); ν_{max} 3 240 (NH), 1 720–1 710 (CO of α -pyrone), 1 680–1 665 (CO of acid hydrazide), 1 350–1 365 (C=S) and 1 605 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 6b (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.1 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (2H, q, NCH₂), 3.4 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 6.5–7.3 (4H, m, ArH), 9.6 (2H, br s, NHCSNH) and 10.2 (1H, br s, CONH); δ 6c (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.3 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 6.5–7.4 (9H, m, ArH), 9.7 (2H, br s, NHCSNH) and 10.3 (1H, br s, CONH); 6a, m.p. 190°; b, 195°; c, 180°.

2-Alkylamino-5-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxomethyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (7a, b): The thiosemicarbazide (6a, c; 0.01 mol) was added with stirring to anhydrous phosphoric acid (20 ml) during 20 min and the mixture was heated on an oil-bath at 120° for 0.5 h. The slurry was then poured over ice-water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: ν_{max} 3 215–3 200 (NH), 1 715 (CO of α -pyrone), 1 630 (C=N) and 1 605 cm^{-1} (C=C); 7a, m.p. 295°; b, 240°, δ (CF_3COOD) 2.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.4 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 6.5–7.5 (9H, m, ArH) and 10.4 (1H, br s, NH).

Formation of 7a, b from 5: A mixture of 5 (0.01 mol) and alkyl (Me/Et/Ph) isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. It was then cooled and poured in water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 7a, b.

5-Mercapto-4-alkyl-3-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxomethyl)-1,2,4-triazoles (8a, b): Compound 6b/c (0.01 mol) was refluxed with NaOH solution (4%, 25 ml) for 3 h. The resulting solution was treated with charcoal, filtered and cooled. The filtrate was acidified with HCl to pH 5–6. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol: ν_{max} 3 230 (NH), 2 580 (SH), 1 720 (CO of α -pyrone), 1 625 (C=N), 1 605 (C=C) and 1 325 cm^{-1} (C=S); 8a (70%), m.p. 240°; δ (CF_3COOD) 1.2 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.0 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.4 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 3.8 (2H, q, NCH₂) 4.6

NOTE

(1H, br s, SH), 6.5–7.3 (4H, m, ArH) and 9.8 (1H, br s, NHCS); **b** (73%), 260°; δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.5 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 4.7 (1H, br s, SH), 6.4–7.4 (9H, m, ArH) and 9.9 (1H, br s, NHCS).

5-Methylthio-4-alkyl-3-(4-methyl-2-oxo-2H-1-benzopyran-7-yloxomethyl)-1,2,4-triazoles (9a, b): To a suspension of **8a/b** (0.01 mol), fused sodium acetate (2 g) and methyl iodide (0.01 mol) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 6 h, then cooled to room temperature and poured in ice-water. The resulting white solid was crystallised from methanol: $\nu_{\max}$ 1715 (CO of α -pyrone), 1630 (C=N) and 1605 cm⁻¹ (C=C); **9a** (65%), m.p. 160°; δ (CDCl₃) 1.2 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.6 (3H, s, SCH₃), 3.3 (2H, br s, OCH₂), 3.9 (2H, q, NCH₂) and 6.4–7.3 (4H, m, ArH); **b** (63%), 140°; δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.67 (3H,

s, SCH₃), 3.4 (2H, br s, OCH₂) and 6.5–7.4 (9H, m, ArH).

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